

Table 1: Repository software solutions used by selected research Universities worldwide (informed by Re3Data)

Institution	Research data repository	Research publication repository
University of British Columbia	Dataverse(Abacus)	Dspace(cIRcle)
Edinburgh University	Dspace(DataShare)	Dspace(ERA)
Harvard University	Dataverse	Dspace(DASH)
Oxford University	Fedora (ORA-Data) Repository under construction	Fedora(ORA-Data)
University of Essex	Eprints	Eprints
University of Liverpool	Eprints	Repository under construction
University of Munich	Eprints	Eprints
MIT	Dspace or Dataverse	Dspace
TU Berlin	Dspace	Dspace
University of Wisconsin	Dspace(MINDS)	Dspace(MINDS)
Cambridge University	Dspace Repository under construction	Dspace Repository under construction
University of Pretoria	Dspace	Dspace
University of Toronto	Dataverse (Ontario Council of University Libraries)	Dspace(Tspace)
York University	Dspace(Yorkspace)	Dspace(Yorkspace)
Johns Hopkins	Dataverse	Dspace
University of Queensland	Fedora(UQ eSpace)	Fedora(UQ eSpace)
University of Copenhagen	Dataverse(DataBox)	Subject specific only
Peking University	Dataverse	Eprints
University of Western Australia	Dspace(RDO)	UWA research repository
University of Auckland	Figshare	Dspace
Brunel University	Figshare	Dspace
Melbourne University	Figshare	Dspace
University of Amsterdam	Figshare Repository under construction	Fedora(UvA-DARE)
Stockholm University	Figshare	DiVA Swedish universities pubs repository - software unknown